

Oct. 28-2000

Roberta

I worked with John Westman for 11 years. We traveled all over the country and I might even say over the globe. John is the perfect accompanist.

He has such knowledge of the repertoire and knows how to impart his knowledge to his fellow artists and his students.

He always went to the theater before a performance to check the piano and the lights and he was such a joy to travel with and to sleep